

The Confluence of Historical Revisionism, Political Radicalism, and Militarism in Contemporary Russian-Imperial Culture: A Time-Sensitive Network Perspective

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1. Research problem & context

Analyse how historical revisionism, political radicalism, and militarism intersect in Putin's neo-imperial culture.

Show that this is not a purely "internal Russian" phenomenon but a hub in a global radical-right ecosystem.

2. Theoretical background & previous work

- Build on the earlier paper (Werner–Dieriabin–Vovchuk) mapping networks of people, organisations, media and states.
- Starting claim: Russian political radicalism is largely a Russianised adaptation of Western far-right and Christian Right ideas, not an isolated invention.

FORMATION PECULIARITIES OF THE RUSSIAN POLITICAL RADICALISM (2012 – 2024)

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3. New contribution of this study

Extend the analysis to state-level networks (state-to-state SNA).

Introduce a time-sensitive approach with four periods:

- 1945–1991
- 1991–2014
- 2014–2022
- After 2022 (preliminary results)

Main question: How does Russia's structural position in this network evolve across these periods?

4. Data & method

- Corpus of ~145 scholarly and journalistic sources → manually coded influence relations (Auth: Antoni Dieriabin, supervised by Wiktor Werner)
- Aggregation to state of origin → state of influence.
- Directed graphs for each period.
- Metrics:
 - 1) density, reciprocity, degree assortativity,
 - 2) node-level centralities (strength, betweenness, closeness, combined centrality score),
 - 3) share of edges involving Russia (by count and weight),
 - 4) strength concentration (max / mean).

5. Key results:

- 1945–1991: multipolar, relatively dense network; Russia/USSR important but not dominant; moderate centralisation.
- 1991–2014: expansion + Russia as a super-hub; high reciprocity, intensive exchange; over 60% of total edge weight involves Russia.
- 2014–2022: network becomes sparser, hub–periphery pattern strengthens; about half of all ties involve Russia → stabilised dominance.
- After 2022: small, narrow core; low reciprocity, nearly 70% of total edge weight involves Russia; Russia as primary broadcaster, not a symmetric partner.

Flows to/from Russia by period (state-level, %)

Legend for grey numbered nodes – 1945 1991:

- 1 → Argentyna
- 2 → Austria
- 3 → Greece
- 4 → Japan
- 5 → Kuba
- 6 → Romania
- 7 → Sweden
- 8 → Switzerland

1991-2014 - state-level influence network

Legend for grey numbered nodes – 1991–2014:

- 1 → Brasil
- 2 → Chile
- 3 → Georgia
- 4 → India
- 5 → Irlandia
- 6 → Moldovaia
- 7 → New Zealand
- 8 → Poland
- 9 → Portugalia
- 10 → Romania
- 11 → Serbia
- 12 → Sweden
- 13 → Switzerland

2014-2022 - state-level influence network

Legend for grey numbered nodes – 2014-2022:

- 1 → Austria
- 2 → Bułgaria
- 3 → Chile
- 4 → Georgia
- 5 → India
- 6 → Japan
- 7 → New Zealand
- 8 → Norway
- 9 → Poland
- 10 → Spain
- 11 → Sweden
- 12 → Syria
- 13 → Ukraine

after 2022 - state-level influence network

After 2022 (preliminary results)!

6. Metrics

Network density by period

Reciprocity by period

Degree assortativity by period

6. Metrics

7. Interpretation

Trajectory from:

Russia as one important actor among many (Cold War), through a phase of mutual learning and exchange (1990s / early 2000s), to a position as main exporter of a neo-imperial ideological package (after 2014, very probably after 2022).

Structural change mirrors:

- 1) the conservative turn,
- 2) consolidation of the “Russkiy mir” doctrine,
- 3) militarisation of education and memory politics,
- 4) legitimisation of imperial violence.

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